

Shall Parents Be A Better Co-Therapist?

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Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterised by impairments in social communication and interaction and repetitive restricted behaviours (Hodis et al., 2025). It is observed in individuals across various social groups. Children with ASD may experience challenges in adaptive functioning and the severity of symptoms can vary widely. The comorbid physical and mental disorders include intellectual disability, seizures, anxiety and emotional disturbances, which are more common in ASD. These challenges can lead to reduced quality of life for individuals with ASD, their families and society. Involving parents in their child's treatment for autism spectrum condition is crucial. The Parents who participate in an individualised therapy for their child in collaboration with a therapist provide a healthy support system. Parents are the most effective therapists for improving a child's prognosis because they are the individuals with whom a child spends the most time. Numerous researchers have highlighted the significant positive impact parents have on the development of social and emotional well-being. This article focuses on the major role of parents in raising a child with Autism Spectrum Disorder.

Keywords: Autism spectrum disorder, parental involvement, emotional adaptation, intervention.

The term "autism" was coined by Eugen Bleuler in 1911 to describe the extreme social withdrawal and self-centeredness sometimes present in patients with schizophrenia (Hodis et al., 2025). The condition ASD consists of a diverse set of varying degrees of difficulty with social interaction and communication, as well as atypical activity and behaviour patterns. Common traits include challenges with transitioning between activities and an intense focus on unusual sensory responses. Early diagnosis before 2 years of age brings a good prognosis for the child (World Health Organization, 2025).

The needs and abilities of children with Autism are broad and dynamic. Some achieve independence, while others require extensive, lifelong support due to the severity of the condition. Autism often impacts education and employment prospects. The quality of life for individuals with Autism is significantly influenced by societal attitudes and the support structures provided by families, communities, and authorities (Pfeiffer et al., 2022).

Many children with Autism have co-occurring conditions like epilepsy, emotional disturbances, anxiety and Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) (World Health Organization, 2025). The spectrum of intellectual functioning among those with autism is wide, encompassing everything from profound impairment to superior intelligence (Pfeiffer et al., 2022).

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The Prime Features of Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD)

Early Diagnosis of Red Flag

The early signs of ASD include (Webb & Jones, 2009):

- Even at the age of 12 months, not responding to their name call
- Unable to point out objects even at the age of 14 months
- Lacks or decreased interest in "pretend play" even by the age of 18 months

General Signs

- Eye contact will not be maintained adequately
- The child prefers to be alone
- Struggles to articulate and comprehend their emotions
- Impaired language and communication abilities (repeating words or phrases, responding to inquiries with irrelevant information)
- Getting agitated over small adjustments
- Compulsive behaviours
- Performing repetitive motions or responding strangely to stimuli

Parental Adaptation Phases

The diagnosis of the child makes a greater impact on the emotional well-being of the parents. To overcome their trauma, they undergo various phases of adaptation. It is not a compulsion that they must go through all the phases in the same order. They may skip some stages or jump from one phase to another. The phases of adaptation are as follows:

- Denial
- Anxiety
- Bargaining
- Depression
- Adaptation

The Need for Parents to be Therapists

Children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) can significantly improve their developmental outcomes if they receive intense therapy for more than 20 hours per week as individual behavioral therapy across years (Dawson & Bernier, 2013; Reichow, 2012). However, some families might not find this approach's practicality helpful (Nevill, Lecavalier, & Stratis, 2018).

Some of the factors contributing to increased parental stress for those with young children include early diagnosis (Moh & Magiati, 2012), difficulty accessing treatment services (Carter et al., 2009), and the severity of the child's problem (Zaidman-Zait et al., 2014).

Children who receive intense treatment appear to improve considerably more than those who receive less treatment, according to research (Anderson et al., 1987). Parents could very well be the best people to train them in a natural environment. The training given to parents will enhance their confidence in dealing with their child's behaviour at home.

Benefits of Parent Involvement

As "co-therapists," the parents provide regular interaction and guarantee that the child's intervention is suitable for social interactions. It has been shown that providing parents with group training in new skills can help them support one another. We can more effectively assist their child's growth by assessing the effectiveness and efficiency of parental involvement in educational programs.

Key components of effective teaching include: the child's developmental progress, parent-child interaction patterns, parents' knowledge, attitudes and stress levels, family functioning, and cost-benefit therapies.

Parental involvement enhances family dynamics in addition to helping the child. It has been identified that parents who are included in treatment have shown reduced stress levels, increased positive affect and improved self-efficacy.

What is Structured Teaching?

Structured teaching is a system for organizing the environment of the child, developing new activities and making the child understand what is expected from them. It is clearly used to increase the child's independent functioning. The major focus in structured therapy is the physical structure and visual schedules.

Practical Strategies for Parents

Environmental Organization: Show the child where to put his/her belongings by labelling their shelves or cupboards.

Visual Cues for Self-Help Routines: While the child is indulging in self-help routines like brushing of teeth, bathing or handwashing, describe each step verbally and make sure that pictures do a lot of talking near the activity area. Visual cues help the child process information for a longer duration than oral instructions.

"Talking Time": Having a "Talking Time" in their routine will help them improve their communication. While teaching the child with Autism, GO SLOW and SHOW (i.e., show & teach with real objects, with actions & gestures, with pictures & with printed words).

Child-Centered Approach: Teach the way the child wants to learn, instead of teaching them what you prefer to teach.

Everyday Learning Opportunities: Even simple routines could become effective teaching opportunities. Helping parents in the kitchen brings chances for the child to develop counting, sorting,

balance, coordination and thinking skills.

Sensory Regulation: A deep tactile pressure of arms, legs and body could help the child with ASD to calm down (e.g., a big firm hug). Low swinging with gentle pushing front and back will help them.

Conclusion

Parents, teachers and therapists have many resources available to train the child with Autism Spectrum Disorder. At times, incorporating so much learned information seems overwhelming for many. There is no one effective strategy to teach the child. It is about incorporating many techniques to find the best working model for the child. Tailoring the treatment modules for individuals could be best analysed by the parents. By working together, we can effectively bring a good prognosis for the child.

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